

ELASTIC AND INELASTIC MODELLING OF CORRUGATED CARDBOARD

S. Allaoui¹, Z. Aboura², and ML Benzeggagh¹

¹ *Laboratoire Roberval de mécanique, Université de technologie de Compiègne
B.P. 20529 F - 60205 Compiègne Cedex France*

² *L3M. IUT de Tremblay en France Paris 8 –
Rue de la Râperie 93290 Tremblay-en-France, France*

SUMMARY: Due to their periodic structure, an analytical model related the behaviour of the corrugated cardboard is developed. This model is based on classical laminate plate theory and takes into account the geometrical and mechanical properties of the corrugated cardboard constituents. The elastic homogeneous characteristics of the material and its behaviour were approached. This approach permits us to have numerical studies, which take less time computing.

KEYWORDS: corrugated cardboard, sandwich, modelling, behaviour

INTRODUCTION

The principals functions of the packing are to protect what it sells and sell what it protects. One of the more used packing is the corrugated cardboard. This is due to its numerous advantages notably the protection of the environment (completely recyclable) and it's reduced coast. Its applicability extends beyond the packaging while being interested, for example, to the habitat.

Nevertheless, its use in optimum manner requires the knowledge of its mechanical behaviour: elastic, inelastic, failure...

The corrugated cardboard is an orthotropic sandwich with the surface plies (facing) providing bending stiffness, separated by a lightweight bending core (fluting) that provides shear stiffness. Two main directions characterise this material. The first noted MD (machine direction) corresponds to the direction of manufacturing of the material. It coincides with the x axis. The second noted CD (cross direction) corresponds to the transverse direction and coincides with the y axis (Fig.1). Aboura and al. have developed an approach regarding corrugated cardboard as monolithic material and have adapted simple's mechanical tests to characterize this material [1,2]. Several authors proposed a numerical homogenisation of the structure [3,4].

Figure 1. Cardboard panel geometry

This study proposes to replace the corrugated cardboard by an equivalent orthotropic layer. This approach will permit after homogenization to simplify the numerical calculation (Fig.2). First, an analytical model is developed to predict elastic behaviour. It takes into account mechanical properties and geometrical parameters of the constituents (core thickness, fluting step, skin thickness). After that the model is extended to predict the inelastic of the material. The experimental results obtained from the tests carried out on the skins and the core were used like inputs for analytical model. Then a parametric study will be done. In the end a numerical computation is carried out to compare the results of 2D and 3D meshing.

Formulation of the analytical model

To analyse the elastic behaviour of the corrugated cardboard, the proposed approach is based on the lamination using the classical laminate theory. The model is inspired from Ishikawa et al [5], Aboura [6] and Scida et al. [7] related to the elastic behaviour modelling of woven composites materials.

A unit cell representative of the corrugated cardboard is defined as in figure 1b and considered the skins and the undulated fluting as an assembling of many infinitesimal elements dx of unidirectional lamina oriented at different angles. The classical laminate theory is then applied to each element.

Fig. 2: Approach proposed by the study

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_i \\ M_i \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{ij} & B_{ij} \\ B_{ij} & D_{ij} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_j \\ k_j \end{Bmatrix} \quad (i,j=1,2 \text{ and } 6) \quad (1)$$

in which A_{ij} , B_{ij} and D_{ij} are the in-plane stiffness for each infinitesimal element dx . These are defined by:

$$(A, B, D) = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (1, z, z^2) Q_{ij} dz \quad (2)$$

in which

$$Q_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_x}{1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} & \frac{\nu_{xy}E_y}{1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{yx}E_x}{1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} & \frac{E_y}{1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (i,j=1,2,6) \quad (3)$$

Q_{ij} is evaluated for each constituent of the corrugated cardboard unit cell. This means that the superior and inferior skins and the fluting undulation are taken into account. The local stiffness of each infinitesimal element depends on the constituent elastic properties as well as on the fluting orientation defined by the local off-axis angle $\theta(x)$. This angle is calculated from the fluting median fiber function $Ht(x)$:

$$\theta(x) = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{dHt(x)}{dx} \right) \quad (4)$$

$Ht(x)$ is assumed to be of sinusoidal form with a maximum thickness of hc :

$$Ht(x) = \frac{hc}{2} \sin \left(2\pi \frac{x}{P} \right) \quad (5)$$

Once the Q_{ij} terms are calculated, the in-plane stiffness coefficients can be evaluated for each element in different regions of the unit cell by using equation (2).

Figure 3: Unit cell representative (VER) of the corrugated cardboard

The global matrices A_{global} , B_{global} and D_{global} for the corrugated cardboard unit cell are calculated numerically from the local matrices A , B and D evaluated for each infinitesimal element with an average in the x direction by:

$$(A, B, D)_{\text{globale}} = \frac{1}{P} \int_0^P A(x), B(x), D(x) dx \quad (6)$$

From the global matrices $[A]$, $[B]$ and $[D]$, the effective Young's modulus, shear modulus and Poisson's ratio of the corrugated cardboard can be obtained.

Results of homogeneous elastic properties

Two layers and one flute compose the corrugated cardboard used for the study. The mechanical characteristics of the constituents are obtained by tensile tests according to experimental protocols developed in precedent studies [1,8]. They are shown with the geometrical characteristics in the table 1.

Table 1: Mechanical and geometrical characteristics of the sandwich constituents

	h (mm)	E_{MD} (Mpa)	E_{CD} (Mpa)	ν_{xy}	ν_{yx}
Upper layer	0.235	4514.53	1895.83	0.282	0.215
Flute	0.235	4703.75	1854.3	0.353	0.088
Lower layer	0.19	4458.6	1944.5	0.277	0.115

After that the model was used to evaluate the homogeneous characteristics of the sandwich. Table 2 show the results of the homogenization. We note that the model results are in good agreement with the experience. All the analytical homogeneous characteristics are given with an error less than 10% compared to the experimental ones. The Poisson ratios ν_{xy} and the Young modulus in the cross direction are estimate with a maximal error of 5%, wherever the Young modulus in the machine direction and Poisson ration ν_{yx} are estimated with an error around 8%. This error is due to the effect of the process of manufacture of corrugated cardboard. Fig. 4 shows this effect, which is produced by the drum during the manufacture.

Table 2: Comparison between experimental and model results

	E_{MD} (Mpa)	E_{CD} (Mpa)	ν_{xy}	ν_{yx}
Experimental characteristics	656	412.38	0.251	0.125
Model results	711.99	391.47	0.246	0.135
Model / Exp. (%)	8.53	-5.07	-1.87	8.33
Model results after correction	676.1	390.78	0.246	0.142
Model after correction / Exp. (%)	3.06	5.24	-1.87	13.88

To evaluate it, we determined the mechanical characteristics of the skins before and after manufactured of the corrugated cardboard. We carried out micro tensile tests on skins gives by the manufacturer and skins extracted on the structure. The tests were carried out in the cross and machine direction. We found that the manufactured process does not affect the characteristics of the lower layer and the flute, when the upper layer loses 13% of its characteristics in the machine direction. After that we have use the news mechanics characteristics of the upper layer as inputs for the analytical model. We note that the error in estimation of the Young modulus in the machine direction passes from 8.53% to 3.06%. In the same time the other characteristics do not evolve significantly.

Figure 4: crushing of the upper layer

Modelling of the inelastic behaviour

The analytical model developed previously was carried out in the elastic range. Beyond this elastic part, the corrugated cardboard has viscoelastic behaviour. The extension of the analytical model to the simulation of the behaviour beyond elasticity requires the knowledge of the behaviour laws of the components of corrugated cardboard. In a first approach, the model will be fed by the experimental results resulting from the tests carried out on the layers and the flute. The model will be extending to the prediction of non-linear uniaxial tensile behaviour of the material. This extension needs to know the stress-strain curve in MD and CD of the sandwich constituents. Assuming strain continuity, the local stress is computed in each element of the unit cell at every increment of macroscopic stress by using the stress-strain curves of the skins and fluting. A new stiffness is then determined. By homogenisation on all unit cell, the global stiffness can be calculated and then the prediction of non-linear behaviour of the corrugated cardboard.

Fig. 5 shows a good agreement between the behaviour simulated by the model in the machine direction and the experimental results one. On the other hand the agreement is worse in the cross direction. Indeed after having approached elastic phase correctly, the model overestimates the inelastic phase.

This phenomenon is due to the effect of the interface between the two skins and the flute. This interface intervenes when the material is requested mechanically. It is made up of starch, which is used as adhesive between the tops of the flute and the skins. During the tensile test, the request of the interface causes a local damage due to the high rigidity of the starch compared to the cardboard. This phenomenon does not interfere in the machine direction

Figure 5: Comparison between experimental and model results. MD uniaxial tensile test.

because the flute is requested very little and the skins govern the response of the sandwich. This phenomenon is not taken into account by the model.

After the validation of the model, a parametrical study, which highlights the effect of the structural parameters on elastic and inelastic behaviour of the material, was carried out. The studied parameters are: fluting step (P), layers thickness (hl), core thickness (hc) and flute thickness (hf). Each parameter was varied from $\pm 10\%$, $\pm 20\%$, $\pm 30\%$, $\pm 40\%$ and $\pm 50\%$.

Fig. 6 a and b show that the behaviour of material is more sensitive to the thickness evolution of the skins in the machine direction than in the cross direction. A reduction of -50% on the thickness skins involves a fall of 33% and 24% on respectively the Young modulus in the MD and CD (fig. 10 a and b).

The thickness of each layer is lower than one millimetre. An error of measurement of 10% corresponds to a value of 0.0235mm and will involve a fall of almost 6% . Therefore a detailed attention for the measurement of the thickness and the choice of the instrument is advised.

Contrary to layers thickness, the variation of the flute thickness affect more the behaviour of material in the CD than in the MD (fig. 7 a and b). Therefore the behaviour of corrugated cardboard in tensile is governed by the skins in the machine direction and the flute in the cross direction.

Figure 6: Parametric study according to the layers thickness.

Figure 7: Parametric study according to the flute thickness.

The reduction of core thickness causes the reduction of the total thickness of corrugated cardboard. This configuration tends towards that of paperboard. This involves an increase in rigidity in both directions (fig. 8 a and b). This effect is more perceptible in the MD whereas in the CD it is perceptible only beyond an increase of 30% of the thickness.

The same report is made when the core thickness increases. In the machine direction, we note a reduction of rigidity with an effect less significant than previously. On the other hand in the CD we note an increase in rigidity starting from an evolution of 20% of the core thickness, whereas we would have to have the reversed effect (fig. 8b). This is due to the compensation of the previous effect by the influence of flute. By increasing the core thickness, we increase the length of the flute in our sandwich, which causes an evolution of the core rigidity.

Fig 10a shows that the evolve of the flute step has not an effect on the behaviour of material in the MD. The increase of the step involves a loss of rigidity in the CD (fig 10b). On the other hand by decreasing this parameter we note a more significant effect on the behaviour of material. This effect is due to the fact that the increase of the step induces increases of the flute length, which has an effect on the behaviour of material in the CD.

Figure 8: Parametric study according to the core thickness.

Figure 9: Parametric study according to the fluting step.

Figure 10: Evolution of the mechanical characteristics according to the thin of the layers.

Numerical simulation

In order to assess the relevance of the homogenisation method developed for this purpose, a finite element analysis is used. The main goal is to verify the possibility to use a 2D meshing of the corrugated cardboard, instead of a 3D meshing extensively used in the literature [4].

A finite element model is created for the 3-point bending. The applied load is 5N. The geometrical characteristics of this model are chosen similar to those used in the corresponding experiments. The used element is the basic triangular 3-nodes flat shell. Table 3 presents a comparison between experimental and the two finite element approaches results.

The agreement between experimental and the two FE approaches is correct. We note that the bending stiffness are estimate with an error of 8.5% and 12% respectively in the machine and the cross direction. For the 3D meshing the stiffness is estimate with an error of 7.86% in the cross direction. However, for an overall behaviour, the time calculation of the 2D approach is 10 times lower than that of the 3D approach. It appears that the simplified homogenisation procedure is adequately accurate and fast for effectively analysing corrugated cardboard panel in the preliminary and optimisation design stages.

Table 3: Comparison between FE and experimental results

	2D Approach MD	2D Approach CD	3D Approach CD	Exper. CD	Exper. MD
Bending rigidity (N/mm)	3.68	2.017	2.47	2.29±0.09	3.39±0.36
CPU Time (s)	0.3	0.3	3	/	/

Conclusion

This study falls under a series of work devoted to the study of the mechanical behaviour of the corrugated cardboard. It purposes an analytical model, which gives the elastic homogeneous parameters of the sandwich. The model makes it possible to approach well the elastic behaviour of the material when the effect of the interface of the layers and the flute is taken into account.

Then the model was extending to predict the inelastic behaviour. The parametric study shows that the behaviour of the corrugated cardboard in tensile is governed by the skins in the machine direction and the flute in the cross direction.

Another effect was noted. By increasing the core thickness or by decreasing the flute step, the flute length increases. This led to an increase in the core rigidity and thus the material rigidity in the direction CD

In order to assess the relevance of the homogenisation method developed for this purpose, a finite element analysis is used. The main goal of this work is to verify the possibility to use a 2D meshing of the corrugated cardboard, instead of a 3D meshing extensively used in the literature. It was found that the simplified homogenisation procedure is adequately accurate and fast for effectively analysing corrugated cardboard panel in the preliminary and optimum design stages.

REFERENCES

1. Aboura Z., Talbi N., Allaoui S. and Benzeggagh M.L. "Elastic behaviour of corrugated cardboard: Experiments and Modelling", *Composite Structures*, 2004, 63, 53-62.
2. Aboura Z., Allaoui S. and Benzeggagh M.L. "Etude et modélisation du comportement élastique d'une structure sandwich de type carton ondulé", *JNC 13, Strasbourg* 2003, 1027-1036.
3. Buannic N., Cartraud P. et Quesnel T. "Homogenization of corrugated core sandwich panels", *Composite Structures*, 2003, 59, 299-312.
4. El Damatty A.A., Mikhael A and Awad A.A, "Finite element modeling and analysis of a cardboard shelter", *Thin-Walled Structures* 2000, 38, 145-165.
5. Ishikawa T, Chou TW. « Stiffness and strength behavior of woven fabric composites", *Journal of Material Science*, 1982, 17, 3211-3220.
6. Aboura, Z., Chouchaoui, C.S. and Benzeggagh, M.L., "Analytical model of woven composite laminate. Superposition effect of two plies", *ECCM 6*, 1993, Bordeaux.
7. Scida, D., Aboura, Z., Benzeggagh, M.L. and Bocherens, E., "Prediction of elastic behaviour of hybrid and non-hybrid woven composite", *Composites, science and technology*. 1997, 57, 1727-1740
8. Allaoui S., Aboura Z. and Benzeggagh M.L. "Influence des conditions environnementales sur le comportement mécanique de structure sandwich de type carton ondulé", *JNC 14, Compiègne, Mars* 2005, 1165-1174.